

**BIOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF ENDOPHYTIC FUNGI
OF UZBEKISTAN IN PANCREATIC LIPASE
INHIBITION****Maftuna Mengbutayevna Yuldosheva****PhD, Acting Associate Professor, University of
Business and Science, Tashkent, Uzbekistan****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20589248>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 26th May 2026Accepted: 28th May 2026Online: 30th May 2026**KEYWORDS**

In this regard, the aim of the present study was to investigate the pancreatic lipase inhibitory activity of endophytic fungal strains isolated from different plant organs, including roots, bulbs, stems

ABSTRACT

According to a recent report by the World Health Organization, more than one billion adults worldwide are overweight, of whom approximately 300 million suffer from obesity [1]. One of the therapeutic approaches to obesity prevention is to reduce the absorption of fatty acids through the inhibition of lipase activity in the digestive system [2]. Currently, the only anti-obesity drug approved worldwide is Orlistat, a lipase inhibitor. However, its long-term use is associated with serious adverse effects, including hepatotoxicity, gallstones, kidney stones, and acute pancreatitis.

According to a recent report by the World Health Organization, more than one billion adults worldwide are overweight, of whom approximately 300 million suffer from obesity [1]. One of the therapeutic approaches to obesity prevention is to reduce the absorption of fatty acids through the inhibition of lipase activity in the digestive system [2]. Currently, the only anti-obesity drug approved worldwide is Orlistat, a lipase inhibitor. However, its long-term use is associated with serious adverse effects, including hepatotoxicity, gallstones, kidney stones, and acute pancreatitis [3].

Therefore, there is a growing need to identify natural sources for the development of safe and effective anti-obesity agents. Endophytic fungi, which inhabit the internal tissues of plants, represent a rich and promising source of biologically active compounds. Numerous studies have demonstrated that endophytes associated with medicinal plants produce metabolites capable of inhibiting pancreatic lipase and may serve as valuable candidates for the development of anti-obesity drugs [4].

In this regard, the aim of the present study was to investigate the pancreatic lipase inhibitory activity of endophytic fungal strains isolated from different plant organs, including roots, bulbs, stems, leaves, and inflorescences of local medicinal plants such as Jerusalem artichoke, Turkestan mint, asafoetida (*Ferula assa-foetida*), and serrated onion (*Allium* spp.). Metabolites were extracted from the fungal biomass according to the method of Lang et al., with modifications introduced by Hazalin et al. [5]. The inhibitory activity was evaluated using a qualitative assay based on phenol red, a pH-sensitive indicator that changes color in the inhibition zone [6].

The results demonstrated that the level of pancreatic lipase inhibition exhibited by the extracts of the studied endophytic fungi ranged from 27.5% to 51.7%. Under the experimental conditions employed, the inhibitory activity of the reference standard Orlistat was 51.7%.

Overall, the findings indicate a significant pancreatic lipase inhibitory potential of metabolites produced by endophytic fungi associated with local medicinal plants and highlight their promise as a source of natural anti-obesity agents.

References:

- 1.Arbeeny CM. Addressing the unmet medical need for safe and effective weight loss therapies. *Obesity Research*. 2004;12:1191–1196.
- 2.Khaodhiar L, McCowen KC, Blackburn GL. Obesity and its comorbid conditions. *Clinical Cornerstone*. 1999;2:17–31.
- 3.Heck AM, Yanovski JA, Calis KA. Orlistat, a new lipase inhibitor for the management of obesity. *Pharmacotherapy*. 2000;20(3):270–279.
- 4.Gupta M, Saxena S, Goyal D. Potential pancreatic lipase inhibitory activity of an endophytic *Penicillium* species. *Journal of Enzyme Inhibition and Medicinal Chemistry*. 2015;30:15–21.
- 5.Hazalin NA, Ramasamy K, Lim SM, Wahab IA, Cole ALJ, Majeed AA. Cytotoxic and antibacterial activities of endophytic fungi isolated from plants at the National Park, Pahang, Malaysia. *BMC Complementary and Alternative Medicine*. 2009;9:46.
- 6.Singh R, Gupta N, Goswami VK, Gupta R. A simple staining protocol for lipases and esterases. *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*. 2006;70:679–682.

